

There's History in All Men's Lives

(Ljubljana, 09-26-2023)

Conference Proceedings

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Instead of an editorial

The conference [There's History in All Men's Lives](#), held in Ljubljana on 25–26 September 2023, marked two important events: the tenth anniversary of the first published volume of the New Slovenian Biographical Lexicon and, equally if not even more importantly, the completion of the project [INTAVIA: In/Tangible European Heritage Visual Analysis, Curation & Communication](#), a H2020 research and innovation action funded by the European Commission within the call DT-TRANSFORMATIONS-12-2018-2020 “Curation of digital assets and advanced digitisation” (project ID: 101004825).

Divided into two thematic parts (which were by no means mutually exclusive), the conference brought together experts from various fields ranging from history to cultural history, art history, literary studies ... to various fields of what is most broadly referred to as digital humanities.

While the papers presented on the first day will be published in a separate printed volume (planned in mid-2024), the papers presented on the second day – collected and published in this volume for a wider readership – form part of the effort to produce Deliverable 8.8 ("Conference proceedings").

Among other things, the call for papers stated: “While it may seem that biography has experienced a period of disengagement from the academic world in recent decades, this couldn't be further from the truth. ... The project *InTaVia - In/Tangible European Heritage: Visual Analysis, Curation and Communication* has been working to connect and harmonise these collections across borders, making them accessible and visible to the public.”

This volume of papers, which is intended to be read as a companion to the video lectures posted online (referenced under each title of the respective papers), aims to underline and summarise these efforts.

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Building Knowledge Graphs for DH Data (Example of InTaVia)

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NeCPXEW28Is&list=PLjVKITCVnkiDs9soHWMsINSxwTyB4rxs&index=13>

Abstract

A central outcome of InTaVia is a knowledge graph, which harmonizes and links biographical data from four prosopographical databases across Europe (FI, NL, AT, SI) and connects them to related cultural objects from Wikidata and Europeana. For producing the InTaVia Knowledge Graph the consortium has worked on three major outcomes. The InTaVia Data Model (IDM-RDF), a CIDOC CRM and Bio CRM based ontology used to model the data in the triplestore, pipeline components to convert and enrich the data and a Rest API in front of the triplestore to deliver the data in a simplified and sanitised way to the web application and interested users. The presentation will give an overview of this architecture and discuss pros and cons of the design decisions with regard to other semantic web applications and projects in the field.

This paper is a brief introduction to how the InTaVia knowledge graph is built, how it works and how the ontology is created. Let us start with the aims and objectives of the project. The InTaVia project is an H2020 project involving four countries: Slovenia, Austria, the Netherlands and Finland. Some of the goals of the project were to integrate four national biographical dictionaries – Slovenian, Austrian, Finnish and Dutch – into one data source. Furthermore, the goal was to enrich this data with linked open data and NLP, and to provide an online platform on top of the knowledge graph, using visual analytics to analyse the data. Some of the research questions, or the three main research questions we had were, first, is it possible to integrate these different prosopographical resources and create an almost homogeneous resource; furthermore, can we then use NLP and linked open data to enrich the less rich data points in the graph; and, finally, does visual analytics provide a useful means of analysing such a data set?

The tech stack for the backend that we are presenting here is a FastAPI that provides the REST endpoints for retrieving the data, including Pydantic for type checking so that we provide a type-safe data, the Blazegraph – a triple store as the database backend –, Jinja2 for creating SPARQL queries and Redis for caching the queries so that they are faster.

We are here

Fig. 1: An overview of the whole dataset. The original biographies (left) go into the knowledge graph, followed by the visual analytics studio and the storytelling suite.

We are here

Fig. 2: The backend side of the system; on the left side, we see the object databases and the prosopographical databases, which are serialised into the knowledge graph using Prefect workflows.

For the backend side, the gric API endpoints system was initially used, which we switched for a custom component, built on top of FastAPI. This is then followed by the data curation lab, the VA studio, and all the visual components.

The InTaVia knowledge graph

The InTaVia knowledge graph currently contains about 260.000 person proxies (i.e. datasets on individual persons), 35.000 place proxies, 170.000 CHO proxies (images, letters, cultural heritage objects etc.).

Fig. 3: The four data sets per entity type. On the left, top left, we have the Austrian data, which also contains institutions. Top right is the BiographySampo, the Finnish data. On the bottom, and the Dutch data on the left; Slovenian data is bottom right.

As far as events are considered, the Austrian and Finnish data are more rich, while the Dutch and Slovenian data are less rich in that regard. There are entities across data sets; which do we find in two data sets? There is of course a greater overlap between the Austrian and the Slovenian data, while there is almost none between the Slovenian and Finnish data.

stacked events histogram

Fig. 4: The events histogram. Green represents the biographical events such as birth events, travel events etc. The blue stack is the CHO events.

There is obviously a large gender bias in the dataset. For example, in the Austrian data set there are only about 900 female biographies compared to 17.000 male biographies.

Comparing this gender bias over the centuries, the data (at least in the Austrian data) show a small increase in the proportion of female biographies towards the 20th century.

Looking at the number of events per person, including CHO objects, there are notable cases of people (e.g. in the Austrian and Finnish data) with 2.000 events attached to them; these are mainly people who have written dictionary entries, for example, and all dictionary entries are also found in Wikidata. In terms of the number of events per person, excluding CHO objects, BiographySampo is the richest database, closely followed by the Austrian data and BiographyNet. The Slovenian data currently only includes birth and death events and some CHO events found in Wikidata.

Fig. 5: The InTaVia knowledge graph. Two clusters stand out: the bottom right cluster (orange) is the Austrian data, top left is the BiographySampo data.

How does data flow in our system? We start off with the original data; in the case of Slovenian biographies, we are dealing with TEI, the Finnish data is already CIDOC CRM and the Austrian data a JSON API. We convert that with the Prefect pipelines or on local machines to the target IDM RDF ontology and put that in source named graphs in the triple store.

On top of that we run further enrichment flows using mainly linked open data, creating the InTaVia harmonized named graph which is basically pointing to the source named graphs. Then we have SPARQL queries that query that knowledge graph, convert it to a JSON and return it via the FastAPI to the front end or to the user.

So how does the InTaVia RDF processing actually work? So if you return data from an RDF endpoint, what you get is basically lines of data. So what in the top left is two labels for one person and what the endpoint returns is actually two whole data sets, so it's duplicating the ID of the person and it's in the second row, it's another label then in the first row.

Fig. 6: The InTaVia data workflow.

But what we want to get for the frontend to be easily computable is a nested JSON. So what we have here is in the API a class definition that says our person class has a person attribute which is the ID basically and it has a label attribute which can be a list of strings, so alternative labels, for example and the system that we have, basically, using this definition then constructs this nested version of the data set, where it says then this one person has the one ID, and it has these two labels.

IDM-RDF

The data model for the InTaVia knowledge graph is IDM RDF. IDM refers to the (InTaVia) data model and RDF is the technological base or the generic data model used for building linked data datasets. The data model is based on CIDOC CRM v7.1.1, an ISO standard for modelling cultural heritage data; it's a harmonizing data model and it's based on events. We can think of a person's life as a chain of interlinked events which happen in place and time. We have extended this CIDOC CRM with our own Bio CRM extension which we use for representing the roles of persons in these events. For example, in a production event of a *painting* a person can hold the role *painter*. We can store this kind of semantically rich information. We use RDF named graphs for separating the different data sources, so we can have pieces of information regarding, for instance, the same person in several of these

biographical data sets – but then we want to keep them separated so we can manage them and also keep track of the provenance: which piece of information is coming from which source. We also use EDM – a *Europeana* data model – or an EDM inspired CRM native modelling of cultural heritage data objects. With regards to this, we have made preliminary mapping of our data model to the *Europeana* data model. We have also adopted the Europeana proxy model which is also related to separating the different views coming from different source data sets. We plan to use PROV-O for the modelling of provenance data and BIBFRAME for the modelling of the references and citations of biographies.

A typical event construction used in the InTaVia Knowledge Graph could be roughly sketched as follows: an event, e.g. a painting (or producing a painting) can have a person or any kind of entity in the role of a painter. There can be another person in a different role related to the same event. We can have a time of the event and also the place of the event. All of this interlinks together the different actors and places and times in the knowledge graph.

Fig. 7: IDM-RDF typical event construction.

Fig. 8: IDM-RDF named graphs.

How is entity linking done in practice? We have different kinds of enrichment workflows and basic interlinking practices. For example, in the BiographySampo graph, we have Giuseppe Acerbi, an Italian natural historian, explorer and composer. In the Austrian biography dataset, there is also his biography. So how can we know that these two are the same person and interlink them? Luckily, in the Finnish dataset we have an external identifier, so we have the Wikidata ID of the person Giuseppe Acerbi, and similarly for the Austrian dataset, we have the GND identifier, which is the authority file of the German National Library. So, then we can actually use Wikidata database to query for more information. And actually, in Wikidata there is this very relevant piece of information that this Wikidata entity's GND identifier, is actually the same identifier as the one that's used in the Austrian biography dataset. By using this information, we can actually deduce that these person proxies in these two different biography datasets are actually the same, based on which we can create the kind of integrated person entity for this Giuseppe Acerbi. We can say that these person proxies are connected to the same real-world person.

IDM-JSON

We are delivering JSON for the API and for the consumers instead of RDF. The idea of JSON – why we wanted to provide it – was that front end applications are easy to deal with JSON APIs where it's difficult to use RDF or SPARQL endpoints. We also wanted to have a simplified version of that complex data model shown above. The simplified version basically attaches events like the gender, for example, to attributes of the node, creating a linear node history using the remaining events.

Fig. 9: IDM-JSON schema: CHO objects, places, groups, a node history, which is basically a list of events with time frames and entities attached.

We ended up with a quite complex data model that is everything else but easy to use in practice. It is even more complicated if you include all the provenance data of when was each data point created, with which system etc. Challenges are also the issues of accuracy vs. feasibility, different languages (calling for some automatic translation), a lot of duplicates in the data, and the problem with the performance of the API because triple stores are not exactly performance databases.

Generating Structured Data from Wikipedia Biographies

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GKZxXxzQsgY&list=PLjVKITCVnkieDs9soHWMsINSxwTyB4rxs&index=14>

Abstract

In this talk, we show how Natural Language Processing (NLP) can help to expand and complement the available structured biographical information. We present our publicly available NLP pipeline that automatically extracts entities, relations and events from raw text in English. We explicitly show how we can use this pipeline to discover and extract key events and connections between individuals, organisations and places from Wikipedia. Our pipeline is directly compatible with the InTaVia curation interface and can be used by anyone who is interested in i) extracting structured information from texts via group search (e.g., biographies from several individuals belonging to an art movement) or ii) using Wikipedia biographies to extract general facts about individuals from underrepresented groups.

This paper addresses the question of how to automatically generate a more structured data from English Wikipedia biographies. We use English because, sadly or happily, there are a lot of technological advances in English that allow us to use NLP in an easier fashion – but in principle we can apply the same techniques to other languages. The main (idealistic) goal of taking this approach is to have rich structured biographical data for as many entities as possible, including underrepresented groups or non-canonical people.

In general, can NLP help us with this idealistic goal? So we already have our research question; we would normally want to go to a bunch of digital biographies already, and there are also some very nice resources in Wikidata and Wikipedia. But here, can we use natural language processing to get even more structured information?

Let us employ a use case here. Let's say we want to know a bit more about Ida Pfeiffer, the Austrian explorer. A millennial's first choice would be to go to Wikipedia and find out what is it. There is indeed a long text on **Ida Laura Pfeiffer**; she was born in 1797 in Vienna, Austrian explorer, etc. But the idea of having structured data is: can we have the highlights already: who were the important people in Ida Pfeiffer's life?, what were the most important events? We will use NLP to find out.

There just happens to be a nice resource from the project InTaVia at hand. We can check, what does InTaVia know about Ida Pfeiffer? This is what it will show: there's an entry of Ada Pfeiffer

in the APIS biographical lexicon, it is also in the GND resource. Below, we can see a small network. One place, four events, eleven objects. It's a start. The map displays a little dot – Vienna –, which is nice because she was born there and died there. But wasn't she an explorer? What happened to her world travels? We want to see that. The InTaVia interface presents us with a very nice timeline with events for each year etc. Four events are displayed here, so an obvious question arises: can we get more events in this timeline? We could exploit the German text available in the interface but instead we're going to go to Wikipedia and retrieve this information that we have available in English. Can we find more people, places, or events in the Wikipedia text about Ida Pfeiffer?

Ida Pfeiffer in InTaVia

1 Place
4 Events
1 Person
11 CH-Objects

Fig. 1: InTaVia interface.

The answer is yes. Here is the output of the NLP already displayed in the InTaVia interface with the link to her Wikipedia biography. It yields a richer network, so now we have more places and people involved – and the map looks much better, showing that she went to Madagascar, New Orleans, India etc.

Likewise, we can see more density on the events timeline. Instead of one place, we now have 16; we have 26 events; there are five people shown to have been involved in her life instead of just her in the centre of the network; and there are 15 cultural heritage objects. The density of events also changes: the first event found automatically is that she gave birth to her son Alfred in 1821, then in 1824 the other son, Oscar, later it focuses on her travels etc. until the last event

when she died in 1858. For more context one would have to go deeper into the text, but this is already very helpful.

Relations to places, in this case Vienna where she was born, where she lived, and also where she died, are also listed as well as relations to cultural heritage objects: she wrote the *A Woman's Journey Around the World*, then she wrote *A Lady's Second Journey Around the World* et cetera. As we go down the list, *Descent of Man* appears. But that was by Darwin. Why is it there? We check the biography, and it turns out Darwin cited her Pfeiffer in his *Descent of Man*. This is interesting and it shows she was already *that* famous back in the day. She was even mentioned by Darwin, right?

So it's a pity that the old resources don't have more information about these important women. However, now – with NLP – we can try to bring out more of those people. The next question is: can we visualize any entity in the InTaVia interface? In this case this was an Austrian person – and we have links to Austrian biographies in InTaVia. But the truth is, because we are using Wikipedia, we can really display any person that is featured there.

For example, we looked for Benito Juarez, one of the most famous Mexican presidents. Born in the mountains in Oaxaca, he was a Zapotec; he later learned Spanish, became a lawyer, and then became president in one of the most disturbing moments to live in Mexico. Everyone wanted to invade: Great Britain, France, Spain, even an Austrian emperor! Juarez was the defender of Mexico and became the national hero. We fed his entry into InTaVia, which yields a very dense network, which is completely in line with his frugal life.

Basically, one can display anyone this way! But how do we go about it? First of all, the pipeline (<https://github.com/InTaVia/nlp-pipelines>) is open source. This is the big picture:

Fig. 2: NLP pipeline.

There are three main modules, which can work independently. Let's say you're only interested in getting a bunch of Wikipedia biographies and save them in your computer and then work with that. Sure, just use the blue part. The pink part is NLP systems, some machine learning classifiers that work on English text. That's what we are using to get the structural data. And then the most important part is the green part: now that I have a bunch of structural data, what do we do with it? We can do our own data analysis. We can apply our own use cases, and very importantly, perform evaluation. So, let's talk about how we get data into the InTaVia data model to display it in a neat and orderly way?

For the Wikipedia extraction part, we need a first name and a last name and, ideally, a birth year and a death year so it's easier to disambiguate and make sure we are getting the right person. Some people have the same name. We can also do group search: we can look for, say, all of the people connected to an art movement and retrieve this information from Wikidata, processing biographies for each person entry. It is important to save all of the metadata in Wikipedia, all of the links on the categories, images etc., so we can make use of that later if we need to.

As for the pipelines, we didn't reinvent the wheel. We basically took some state-of-the-art systems for English out there: SpaCy (<https://spacy.io>), FlairNLP (<https://flairnlp.github.io>), AllenNLP (<https://allenai.org/allennlp>) and HeidelTime (<https://github.com/HeidelTime/heideltime>). How did we assemble them together? The idea is: we have raw text on one point and we want to get structured information on the other. So, how do we use the pipeline? These are the colour codes on the next figure will help us get through what each library does:

Fig. 3: English NLP pipeline.

The first step is to *tokenize* the text. We identify the words and then we use *syntactic parsing* to identify sentence boundaries. This is due to processing reasons: one cannot just input a huge chunk of text and expect the classifiers to work. It is important to *identify sentences* so we can have smaller chunks of text and apply the classifiers to that. Then we have six classifiers working in parallel. The first one identifies *time expressions* (e.g. dates, like 31st of March 1851, or “last September” or “two weeks later” etc.). We also have a named entity recognizer which identifies persons, organizations, and places. We have an *entity linker* which tries to disambiguate the identified entities. We have *relation extraction*, so we know persons and we know places and how are they related: did they live in some place?; did they die in some place? We can extract these kinds of basic relations. The blue part is to further enrich the events part; in computational linguistics we like to define *semantic row labelling* as “who-did-what-to-whom”, which is very relevant for biographies. We are exploiting that similarity to extract more events. And, last but not least, there is *coreference resolution*. We don't always refer to a person with their first name: it's not “Ida Pfeiffer did this”, and “Ida Pfeiffer did that” all the time – we also use pronouns. Hence, coreference resolution to link the pronouns to the main entity, which is a way to know who is the subject of the events.

Now we have a bunch of classifiers, so we have to unify them. Enter the “InTaVia Blender” (the green box in Fig. 3). We are basically finding the similarities in the classifier outputs to try

to build events that make sense. We use Wikipedia metadata to help us disambiguate, for example, which is the hardest task in this case. And that's how we end up with structured data.

Let's give some more examples of the outputs. For example, we have here (Fig. 4) the named entity outputs, which give us the persons and the locations, but not much more than that. On the other hand, we have some relations: place of birth, “born in”, and “child of” – and it is linking the entities in the sentence.

But this relation extraction is limited, so that's why we are using also the semantic role labelling output. If you look at the first sentence, it's the same kind of event that was extracted by the relation extractor, but the second sentence wouldn't be identified by a relation classifier, because there is no such relation as “denied”. However, the SRL identifies it, so we can surmise she was denied membership by the Royal Geographical Society in London, because she was a woman. So, we have this relation: “the royal geographical society denied membership to she”. But who is “she”?

Fig. 4: NER output.

This is why we have *coreference resolution*; because of this output we can link it and we can get our clean relation: “Royal Geographical Society denied membership to Ida Pfeiffer”. That's how it gets constructed and the entity linker just gives us the Wikidata outputs.

As we've already mentioned, we can also do group analysis; we can do it with Wikidata queries or we can create our own list on a text file and then just run the pipeline for each person in the list. Instead of having to write our own query in the Wikidata endpoint we can run it here and use, for example, Wikidata as a support for 800 movements of art. For instance, we can use a query to retrieve people related to Art Nouveau; the output in our script found 122 people involved with Art Nouveau. We don't have to do it by hand: the system runs 122 queries of biographies and processes everything and puts it in the file for us. It finds connections between the people that belong to movements etc.

This is, of course, a very pragmatic approach, but there are other things to take into account. NLP outputs are noisy, which we have to bear in mind. The researcher is still the most important part of this pipeline. It is the researcher who decides whether something is true or noise, but this is already of some help.

Generating Structured Data from Biographical Text and Evaluation

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wD-T1hYI9Ik&list=PLjVKITCVnkieDs9soHWMsINSxwTyB4rxs&index=15>

This paper is a little bit about generated structured data from biographical text because it's not so different from the Wikipedia material, but mostly a lot about evaluation because it's important. For a little bit of background, the source that I'll be writing about is the biography portal from the Netherlands, a collection of biographical dictionaries, that is multiple sources written in different times, sometimes nowadays, sometimes two centuries ago. The oldest sources are from the 17th century, and the largest from the 19th and 20th century, and they're all written in Dutch. You're going to see that basically there are good tools for Dutch. It's one of the languages that has more resources than most, but there's only one English in terms of resources, so it's less good than that.

This being Dutch, the events that we extract are a little bit more focused. This is one of the ways that we deal with the quality being a little bit less good. We really focus on typical events from these biographical resources – people, times, and locations – and some of the relations that are very common and very relevant for historians. To give an example (Fig. 1), Anna Maria Schuurman was a so-called house teacher and a poet. In the text we find that there was an education relation where she was a student in theology and that in a time where women were not actually allowed at the university, they made an exception for her and she could sit behind a curtain.

Fig. 1: Example of Anna Maria Shuurman.

And what we get if we do that from a lot of biographies is something like this: we have someone being born, some kind of education information, whether they got married or not, a profession, and, usually, when they died. That is really the focus or the information that is most reliably extracted from these texts. So how is this used? We have these original constructions (Fig. 2), these biographical stories with all kinds of information, and we extract building blocks (Fig. 3), all kinds of pieces of information, with the idea that a historian, or someone who's interested in cultural heritage, can create new objects by looking for patterns across this information. They would create maybe something like Fig. 4, a new structure, something that shows us a new insight based on information that is extracted. Now we're coming to the point of evaluation.

Fig. 2: Original construction.

Fig. 3: Extracting building blocks.

Fig. 4: A new house.

Let's say that we want to evaluate the house and the system output didn't quite look like Fig. 5, what it should have given us, but it looked like Fig. 6. So the house still stands, we can see the shape, but we're missing a couple of pieces. What could also happen, however, is that our system output does something like Fig. 7. This actually has more things correct than the previous message if we look in terms of overlap (Fig. 8), but since it's constructed differently, we will not get the same shape, we will not get the same outcome.

Fig. 5: The new house evaluated.

Fig. 6: The new house evaluated.

Fig. 7: Alternative method.

Fig. 8: Overlap.

Language technology can be used in various applications and it gives us many possibilities, but even though Chat GPT may seem like magic, there is no magic. Language technology can handle more data, find patterns that would not be noticed by a human and support systematic analysis, but it does not guarantee that our analysis are more reliable than a person analysing. Analysis are not better because they are replicable, that is also something that people often say – computers don't make mistakes and we can replicate, or that the errors don't matter because there's so much data that this is just a little bit of noise. The only guarantee that we have is that there will be errors.

Is it more reliable? Computers are better at counting and systematic decisions, and they don't want a specific outcome. They're not expecting to find something and then interpreting that in there. But they can contain and amplify bias. Sometimes the bias of a computer is actually worse. In language technology it often is. And they are still worse at interpreting natural language. So we still evaluate on the interpretations by people.

Replicability: in theory, we can replicate an experiment where we take a pipeline, say, for the Dutch, we run it again, we extract our information and do the same thing. But in practice, it won't always work, and the question is, if replicability makes our research more valid, if we're replicating a bias that is in our system, so if it's just extracting the same wrong things over and over again. It's also good to notice that if we work with systematic data, systematic analysis, we can also replicate what a human does just by carrying out the same resource, or having it carried out by different people.

Another common error is that the big data, the amount of data compensates for errors. What we typically do when we evaluate our tools is that we look at accuracy, how much is correct, or f-score based on some ground truth created by people, and then the assumption is that if

the score is good, it's a very accurate system, then the overall conclusion, the overall pattern will be true. But that is not necessarily the case. It depends on the kind of errors.

I'm going to show some of the examples of things we can do with a biography and show why evaluation matters, and then I will end up with some of the Intavia material.

Rank	BP first results	BP second results
1	Willem I	Willem I (1772)
2	Willem III	Karel V (1500)
3	Prins van Oranje	Willem II (1792)
4	Karel V	Willem III (1650)
5	Willem II	Willem V (1748)
6	Willem V	Domela Nieuwenhuis (1846)
7	Frederik Hendrik	Frederik Hendrik (1584)
8	Domela Nieuwenhuis	Willem III (1817)
9	Willem IV	Lodewijk Napoleon (1778)
10	Prins Maurits	Willem IV (1711)

Fig. 9: Mentions in biographical portal.

One of the things that we did was we looked at who is mentioned most in a biographical portal (Fig. 9). And this is just a ranking based on a very simple method for identifying entities. (I'll come back to this one later.) Why does the count of error manage? A very clear example is if we want to disambiguate locations. There a lot of locations in the Dutch Biographical Portal. We have Amsterdam, there are multiple, one in America, one where I work. If we then disambiguate this in this resource, a very good tactic is to prefer the location in the Netherlands, or near the Netherlands, or closely related to the Netherlands, and we get an accuracy of 97 %, which is extremely high. Hardly any language technology things get that. Now, if we have someone who's investigating where most of the officials who work in Hague are from, these 3 % don't matter, because most probably come from North Holland or South Holland, and that there's 3 % coming from other places that are not in the Netherlands is not going to affect that result. But if we have a historian who is wondering what is the connection between officials that are overseas and the Netherlands, how often did they travel home, did they have relations with people from the Netherlands, this becomes a huge problem, because the former Dutch colonies where they were living would typically have

other locations that at least in these ancient resources will have Dutch names. And in this case, these 3 % are going to directly interfere with the research question.

Another quick example is sentiment detection (Fig. 10). This comes from colleagues of mine who looked at how good different systems are at identifying sentiment. And these numbers are precision and recall. Precision is how many of the things we find are correct, and recall is how many of all the things there were to find did we find. What is important to see is if we look at these systems, the relation of precision and recall between positive and negative is different. And what happens and what is true for most systems is that they tend to over-classify negative examples, so they find more of them, and they also more often classify something as negative that isn't. But the problem is that depending on our exact sample and the data, it will differ how big this difference is. And again, this might matter.

Table 2
Overall Performance of the Tested Sentiment Analysis Approaches

Method	Acc.	α	Positive			Neutral			Negative		
			Pr.	Re.	F1	Pr.	Re.	F1	Pr.	Re.	F1
<i>Machine Learning</i>											
CNN	0.63	0.50	0.68	0.49	0.56	0.58	0.78	0.66	0.72	0.57	0.63
NB	0.58	0.40	0.74	0.34	0.47	0.52	0.83	0.64	0.65	0.47	0.55
SVM	0.57	0.41	0.69	0.37	0.48	0.52	0.79	0.62	0.64	0.48	0.55

Fig. 10: Sentiment detection. (Van Atteveldt et al. (2021))

For example, let's say that what is happening we want to measure some people get more positive or negative, and we see that they were positive and then they get more negative, this is what would be the true outcome (Fig. 11). Our system does something like that. It's still the same pattern, but maybe we were looking for when that happened, and if there's a timeline, and the date where it happened changes, that might matter. More importantly, it could also be that the system output would be the other way around. So we think we're measuring a pattern through time, but we're actually measuring a difference in how well the system can detect sentiment over different time.

Fig. 11: Sentiment analysis.

We have to look at both how well the system is doing, count how much it gets correct, but also what I call extrinsic evaluation, how suitable is it for our use case, and take this hypothesis that we're looking at, or what we want to know as a researcher, to find out what is happening.

Another thing is provenance modelling. We want to know if we use the InTaVia data, what was generated automatically and what was created by people, because the reliability of that will differ. The challenge is, how to convey this message in a current hype.

PER			
Model	Precision	Recall	F1
flair/ner-dutch-large_0.12.2	75.86	91.67	83.02
human_gold	100.0	100.0	100.0
gpt-3.5-turbo	0.5	20.0	0.98
gysbert_hist_fx_finetuned_epoch2	52.48	64.63	57.92
spacy_matcher_nl	27.13	82.72	40.85
stanza_nl	69.77	93.75	80.0

Fig. 12: Differences between tools.

As part of InTaVia, José Angel Daza Arévalo has been building something that I've been wanting to use for a very long time, that is ways to compare outcomes of tools. Fig. 12 shows

state of the art tools, one is the Human Gold. There are annotations by people for Dutch, and the numbers that we see are the precision and recall. We see there are the Flair Dutch entity models doing quite well, precision of 75 % and a recall of 91 %. But still, it's not like for English, and it also partially is related to the data. Some of the other tools that are quite good – Stanza 70 % precision, and 94 % recall. It's already lower and it's clearly lower for English. It's partly because it's Dutch and partly because this data is old. But what Angel did is he's created tools to investigate these differences.

Fig. 13: Investigate differences.

What we see in Fig. 13 is the amount of artworks, identified by different systems. Each of these colours is a different system – only one system finds artworks, the amount of locations found by one system compared to another is different, the amount of persons, Spacy finds a lot of people but Flair NL finds many more locations – so we can really see the overview in pattern and the amount of data that we get out of different tools.

Fig. 14: Revealing differences.

Another thing we can do is compare. Fig. 14 shows what different tools provided as an outcome. We can see that certain entities are identified by multiple tools, the span – some

people take, for instance in Charlotte Sophie Bentinck, the full, and some just take Sophie Banting. We see that von Hessen Homburg is identified as a person name by one tool, but Hessen Homburg as a location by another tool, and we can see the different outcomes of different tools. Or aggregate it (Fig. 15), and then see how many tools identified each span as a person or a location. Green is identified by three tools, and yellow by two, and red by one. This is quite a nice way to get a very quick feeling of what the impact is of choosing one tool over another.

Fig. 14: Combined view.

What Angel also did is he created spreadsheets of overviews of what the tools give as an output, so we can see very quickly where one tool differs a lot from another, either in terms of data and say, okay, there's something with this data because one tool is finding all kinds of locations and another isn't, and also how we can compare the outcome.

The list of the people who are mentioned most, changes, if we create it with different tools. And we do see the top people more or less coming up from most tools, but in the top hundred, there are also definitely people that are not found by all tools. Some tools completely miss out some people in their research, and this is important to know. And another important note is that for Dutch we have multiple tools, but for a lot of other languages we don't. But then we still need to realize that all these errors that we see clearly, because of course these tools cannot all be correct, if we're comparing multiple tools, they also happen if we only have one tool that we're using or looking at.

To conclude, even if we have these amazing tools now, evaluation still matters. The results by Chat GPT on biographical data are not great. We need to think of extrinsic evaluation, what do we want to use it for and what matters for that. And what InTaVia has been contributing is these views that I think are very important to raise awareness, to make people see, that it does matter which tool we use, and also overviews that can help spot potential problems, either because it was the tool we used or with the data.

Relational Knowledge Discovery Based on Wikipedia Links

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gFYnL-J1hSs&list=PLjVKITCVnkieDs9soHWMsINSxwTyB4rxs&index=16>

Abstract

In this project information about the actors in InTaVia datasets is extended by extracting data from their pages in Wikipedia. A network of references is created based on their biographical texts having links to other, related Wikipedia pages. This network with detailed metadata is converted to RDF and can be analyzed programmatically or browsed in a web portal to enlighten research questions such as 1) What are the common features between the national datasets in InTaVia, 2) How does each national network differ from the other ones, or 3) Can we discover serendipitous links connecting the people?

This paper is about the project of Discovering links based on the Wikipedia pages relating to the InTaVia people. First, we will explain about the concept or the background of this idea, presenting some preliminary results of the data analysis made on the results. We will have a look at some work in progress, and point out some guidelines for future work.

Generally, the idea of using Wikipedia was very similar as what other papers in this volume (e.g. José Angel Daza Arévalo) represented. Wikipedia information has been used in one earlier project in Finland called AcademySampo, which was a student register of students in the Royal Academy of Turku, as well as in University of Helsinki in Finland. The idea is to extract the text from the Wikipedia pages and collect the links from there to make a graph out of that so that we have a person who is represented by his Wikipedia page. We have links which are the sentences that are picked from the pages and we have the link target as pages, like in the case of two Finnish artists, Adolf von Becker and Sigrid af Forselles, who both, in their Wikipedia pages, have a mention of a village called Vevey in Switzerland. This creates a kind of graph where the person is attached to the adult based page resource through this sentence. If we take a look at how much Wikipedia pages are available in English as well as in the national languages of InTaVia datasets, we can see that all the datasets are equally represented. If we vice versa chose the German pages, there are plenty of Wikipedia pages in APIS as well as in BiographyNet, but unfortunately the Finnish and the Slovenian pages don't have as many entries.

Of course, there was a lot of data pruning and cleaning like filtering out the kind of links that don't point to any sensible resources. Instead, they point to some disambiguation pages or list of mentioning things or erroneous or outdated or pointing to pages outside Wikipedia.

Some of the aims for this analysis were to find out common features of national datasets, as well as what are some specific features in each national dataset. We will also take a look at the portal under construction. It's based on the Sampo-UI (for more about this subject see Heikki Rantala's paper "Discovering Relations in Knowledge Graphs Using the Sampo Model").

The portal

This portal can visualize the data with charts and maps and data tables and networks. The created dataset, which was converted to relatively simple RDF schema, contained 13.613 actors, where more than half of them were from BiographyNet (7.463), and 3.578 from the Austrian data set (APIS), 2.012 from Finnish BiographySampo, and 708 from the Slovenian biographies (SBI).

Created Dataset in RDF Format

- **13613 Actors**
BiographyNet (7463), APIS (3578), BiographySampo (2012), SBI (708)
- **179712 Sentences**
In average 22.75 references per person extracted from
- **32193 Wikipedia Pages**
7433 People
8962 Geographic Locations
...
Organizations,
Works of Art, Literature, Music
etc.

Fig. 1: The dataset in the RDF format: the number of people is on the Y axis and the number of references is on the X axis.

We can see that most of the pages provide something like from 5 to 10 external links. Of course, there are very well-known national heroes who have pages containing more than 200, maybe 500 references. There are 32.193 pages that we are referring to. We classified them according

to whether the link is pointing to some other people, if it's pointing to geographic location, if it's pointing to some organization, it can be a work of art, it can be a work of literature or music.

Data Analysis

Let's take a look at some results of networks and clusters, as well as some data statistics. A cluster (2D embedding; Fig. 2), shows some clusters from the dataset, and the national biographies are marked with different colours. The darkest, the Dutch BiographyNet has the largest amount of data in this collection all together, so it's widely spread around this 2D embedding. The smaller datasets, like Finnish BiographySampo, seem to have a couple of clusters completely consisting of Finnish data with no or only very few external links to Slovenian data, and plenty of the Slovenian data seem to be in this one cluster, which is however relatively closely connected to the Austrian one.

Fig. 2: Clusters in the datasets.

We also made a brief look at the co-reference network. That's a network created so that two actors are connected when they are pointing to the same Wikipedia page. We can see that the most commonly used network centrality measures pick up some also internationally well-known people like Napoleon, Peter Paul Rubens, Rembrandt, Ludwig van Beethoven, among the actors that have the highest centrality statistics.

We have used five different metrics like the number of links coming into an actor, number of links coming out of that page rank, which was originally developed by Google to find out the

importance or build a recommending system for googling web pages. Hits and hubs classify these actors as hubs, or authorities based on how much data links is coming in or out of that particular node in the graph. As for the analysis about the differences of the mentioned national biographies, are there some terms that are more represented in other ones, which have lower proportion in other national datasets? The fourfold table below (Fig. 3), which we have to read so that the entries that are in the middle of the diagram, shows realism, impressionism and naturalism, revealing that they are relatively equally mentioned in BiographyNet, in BiographySampo, in Slovenian Biography and in APIS. On the other hand, if we get closer to a corner, to the nodes that are in the BiographySampo corner, we see that functionalism is more often mentioned in the Finnish Wikipedia pages than in other ones. And we see in the left corner that art of sculpture and surrealism are more often mentioned in relation to actors in BiographyNet. Choosing these terms of art, most of these results are in the sections for Dutch or for the Austrian national biographies, and there are only a couple of them in the Finnish as well as in the Slovenian sector.

Fourfold Table of Referenced Terms

- Which are the terms that are characteristic to each national dataset?
- Entities related to Art mapped on a Fourfold Table

Fig. 3: Referenced terms.

Another table made with music related entities, we get even more result nodes. If these nodes appear directly on the axis, it means that they have an even amount of mention in some of the datasets.

Work in progress: Portal

In Finland, we have made plenty of web portals based on the SAMPO user interface framework. Generally, the idea is to build this up onto an RDF or linked data publication, and offer different perspectives to observe or research the data; in this case it would be relevant to have one view for the people, one view for the references, and perhaps one for the sentences from where the links are created.

Future work

This was all based on the English Wikipedia, because one way to push this forward would be to also extract the same information from the Wikipedia pages in national languages like German, Dutch, Finnish, perhaps also Swedish in case of Finland and Slovenia. The Wikipedia Python module also allows to extract links vice versa. If there is some place pointing to some actor, we can also get to reverse links. And, of course, to publish the portal.

Heikki Rantala,
Aalto University

Discovering Relations in Knowledge Graphs Using the Sampo Model

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=27ldEDndLlg&list=PLjVKITCVnkieDs9soHWMslNSxwTyB4rxs&index=17>

Abstract

Knowledge graphs represent both explicit and implicit relations between things like persons and places. While the number of potential relations is essentially unlimited, most of such connections are fundamentally uninteresting. For example, two things might both be instances of owl:Thing class, which is a connection, but not an interesting one. Potentially interesting relations can be predefined, and then mined from the knowledge graph using SPARQL CONSTRUCT queries. These relations can be represented as instances and explored using faceted search. While this makes it possible to search connections between two individuals, it also makes it possible to find relations between larger groups, such as connections between persons of a certain profession and places within a certain country.

In discovering relations in knowledge graphs using the Sampo model we are talking about relational search. The basic idea in relational search is finding »interesting« connections between two entities, in this case in a Knowledge Graph. The main word here is »interesting«, because the biggest challenge may be to weed out the uninteresting connections. We are not interested in, for example, that two entities are both persons. If two persons are, for example, related to each other, or if they're a student or teacher, that might be interesting.

We use »knowledge based« method to mine relations from a knowledge graph. We use CONSTRUCT queries that represent interesting connection types, so we have a separate construct query for each of the connection types, for example “student of” or “parent of” or some other connection. There can be also second-degree connections created for example “shared teacher” for two students of the same teacher. We represent these relations as instances of relation class, so each individual relation will be the instance of this relation class. This will make faceted search convenient and fast. But there can also be a lot of relation instances when we get to the second-degree connections, which can be an issue. Obviously, there will be a lot of, for example, teacher-of connections compared to shared teacher connections and so on, so

we need to put some kind of a limit there, but obviously the relations also often get less interesting when the degree grows.

Relations are represented as relation instances that we create with CONSTRUCT queries. The Relations instances have properties such as the type of the relation and the endpoints of the connection, such as two persons. In our demonstrator we are using directed relations, so there is a separate subject and object for the relation. Additionally, there is a property for the relation type, and then the human readable explanation of the connection. Relation instances can also have other properties.

Here (Fig. 1) is an example of the model of the relation instance, there's a type of relation, and then there's a relation subject and relation objects. There's person A and person B, and then there's a person type also, a "student of" relation, and then there is a label that represents the human readable explanation, so A was a student of B, in this case. Then there is a separate instance of relation for each such connection.

Modeling relations

Fig.: Modelling relations.

There can be a huge number of relations like this, even though there should be no obviously uninteresting relations mined. In order for users to search and filter them we have implemented faceted search. Because the entities, for example, the two persons here, can have properties, like occupation (although, in InTaVia, we don't really have consolidated occupations, but we do have some kind of occupations at least), perhaps the country of origin, birthplace, gender,

and so on. This allows us to search relations between larger groups, for example Finnish painters. For example, we selected *Finland* for the country of origin, *painter* for the occupation, and then we can compare if there are more connections for this kind of people to Netherlands or Austria. These relative numbers can be often even more interesting than the individual connections.

There were some issues with harmonization of InTaVia KG (it was a work in progress obviously), and that is why we have struggled a little bit. It had been expected that all the data would be in a uniform format, but this isn't sometimes the case. InTaVia is also currently missing labels for consolidated concepts and any other properties for the consolidated concept. Even though this was a planned feature, this is a problem for faceted search. We needed to create single labels ourselves.

Here (Fig. 2) we have a search of student-teacher relations where the teacher is a person from the Austrian dataset and the student is from the Finnish dataset.

Example of the search in practice

Searching for student-teacher relations where the teacher is a person from the Austrian dataset and student is from the Finnish dataset

The screenshot shows a search interface with a sidebar on the left and a main results area on the right. The sidebar has a search bar and a list of filters for 'Person B country'. The filters are: Austria [391], Slovenia [16], and Finland [4] (checked). The main area shows a table of results with columns for 'Label', 'Hannikainen, Ilmari was student of Franz Schreker', 'Sibelius, Jean was student of Karl Goldmark', 'Nyström, Gustaf was student of Heinrich Frh. von Ferstel', and 'Sibelius, Jean was student of Robert Fuchs' (highlighted in blue). The interface also includes a 'Rows per page' dropdown set to 10 and a pagination indicator '1-4 of 4'.

Fig. 2: Example of a search in practice.

What you can see here is that we've made a selection from the relation type facet. There's the student-teacher relation: we've selected that the teacher is from the Austrian dataset. For the other person's origin, we have selected Finland. Now I should have teacher-student connections where the teacher is Austrian and the student is Finnish. And you can see there are four such relations, for example, Jean Sibelius was a student of Robert Fuchs, and also Jean Sibelius was

a student of Karl Goldmark as well, apparently, and there are a couple of other examples as well.

Of course, these individual relations can be interesting, but again, the more interesting thing can be the relative numbers. We can see that Austria here has a hit count of 391, Slovenia 16 and Finland is 4, which means that the Austrian teachers have much more often Austrian students, which makes sense, Slovenian much less, but still four times more than Finland. This also makes sense, since Slovenia is much closer to Austria than Finland. Even though this is not surprising in any way, it demonstrates how you can compare these numbers, and perhaps when we make a selection of occupations, maybe we will find something surprising there as well.

We are still continuing the work here. Hopefully we can come up with some kind of nice demonstration that can actually be used to find connections between people, especially for people between the countries, but also within the country.

Slovenian Biography as a Biographical Hub and the TEI ENCODING: a Minimalist or Realistic Approach to Semantic Richness of Data?

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XwmzTvsgxA&list=PLjVKITCVnkiaDs9soHWMsINSxwTyB4rxs&index=18>

Abstract

Slovenian Biography is a portal linking the three main Slovenian biographical lexica into a unified resource. The lexicon articles and the biographical data they contain are encoded and structured according to TEI Guidelines. In the presentation, we show the diverse use of TEI encoding as a crucial basis for the life of our biographical portal. We had to find a realistic way between the various possibilities of semantic tagging and the practical needs to achieve the desired result: online publication and widespread use that establishes Slovenian Biography as an indispensable public service of cultural life. However, there are still a number of possibilities for further semantic enrichment.

This paper gives an outline of Slovenian biography in particular as to how we have used the text encoding initiative guidelines to encode the data; in a sense it is a step backwards. Other papers in this volume touch upon quite sophisticated tools for presenting linked data and analysing it. Now, we are stepping downwards in a sense to the preparation of the digital edition, which is a basis for both browsing and reading and subsequent analytical mechanisms. The Slovenian biography portal integrates the three main Slovenian biographical lexica. They contain thousands of biographical articles in a time span of more or less exactly 100 years. I need to outline the path to how our data has become verified, structured and enriched so that a web application can capture and present it in a variety of useful ways. This web app has been operating for exactly ten years now, since 2013. This is, of course, the work of a large team that has been going on continuously since 2007, and I have pointed out here the two people who have been in charge of the technological processes, but the careful editors behind the scenes also deserve a great deal of credit.

The work started with manual OCR text correction, followed by semi-automatic extraction of the person data structured in XML-TEI encoding, which was further manually edited. The cycle of machine data retrieval and manual editing was repeated many times. The result is that for each person, we separated the two:

- a block of structured metadata,
- a block of prose paragraphs, i.e. the original article.

On the left side we see the metadata. What I mean, the left side represents metadata for about 16.000 persons, and on the right, the biographical articles, about ten thousand articles in the three lexica. The diagram (Fig. 1) This diagram shows the structure of the whole portal:

- the three lexica together contain almost 10,000 articles,
- the metadata is compiled for 16,000+ persons.

This means that we have metadata prepared for more persons than there are biographical articles. Those other personalities are, of course, *mentioned* in the full text, and so on. This allows us to insert many links between family members, acquaintances, correspondents, etc.

Fig. 1.: The SB data model.

The final web page therefore shows, at the top, metadata about a person, their variant names, their occupations and the people associated with them.

With the tagging, we have therefore structured the text according to the TEI Consortium Guidelines. Chapter 13 of the Guidelines specifies the use of tags for biographical information,

which we follow quite strictly. And the most important decision that we had to take was which biographical traits to tag. These tags are used to turn a wealth of implicit data into explicit data, ready for processing. The most important decision here was which biographical traits to tag? We decided to choose those which appeared to be of the greatest benefit for the release of the edition and for the user. The bulk of our personal data tagging encodes what the TEI Guidelines refer to as the "states" and "traits" of a person. In contrast, we have not yet encoded events, either personal or historical, although that would probably be interesting. This was a deliberate choice.

Let's have a quick look at some examples of encoding: how we have dealt with a more complex name, as in the case of a 17th century friar. We could have done it a simpler way, as the example (Fig. 2) shows. However, we have established rather firm rules to mark-up names accurately.

TEI encoding: the person-data

•goal: establish firm rules for usage of elements, e.g.:

fra Gregorio Alasia da Sommariva:

```
<persName xml:lang="ita">
  <forename type="monastic">fra Gregorio</forename>
  <surname>Alasia da Sommariva</surname>
</persName>
```

→

```
<persName xml:lang="ita">
  <roleName type="eccl">fra</roleName>
  <forename type="monastic">Gregorio</forename>
  <surname><seg>Alasia da</seg>
    <placeName>Sommariva</placeName>
  </surname>
</persName>
```

Fig. 2: Person-names markup in the SB.

Thus, we have obtained the monastic predicate "Friar" to characterize him as a member of a monastic order, and the friar's birthplace (Sommariva), which is otherwise hidden in his personal name. Personal names often have variant forms. The first personal name is always

canonical as it appears in official written sources. Then follow other, variant names, including pseudonyms and several other kinds of variant names clearly encoded by the attribute "type", such as various acronyms, married name, maiden name monastic names, but also completely incorrect forms of names that need to be labelled, then nicknames, illegal names, etc.

Noble names offer plenty of dilemmas as to how to label the individual parts so as to be correct both onomastically and for practical searches, for example by place. We have produced several typologies which are encoded as taxonomies with subordinate categories. One of these is the typology of kinship relations, which is, against expectations, quite complex. We explicitly encoded the kinship relations as a list of relations.

In conclusion, the TEI encoding ensures that biographical texts can be transformed from a set of implicit data into explicit data, suitable for machine processing. In terms of the large breadth of possible semantic analyses, our encoding can be characterized as minimalist. On the other hand, the obtained encoded data is the foundation of a digital edition of the lexicon that actually works and serves users, and this is a realistic scenario.

The TEI allows us to transfer our data, if necessary, to another application, such as TEI Publisher, which simplifies the display of the texts considerably, as it uses the TEI processing model, which is part of the TEI standard proper. In conclusion, text encoding is by no means a trivial routine, but much more: in my opinion, encoding is a structured display of an editor's knowledge.

This is how we make our lexicon a widely usable and functional resource. In the last year, we have had 164,000 users who have consulted 696,000 documents. Statistics show that the three most viewed biographies include two eminent figures in the field of literature: France Prešeren and Primož Trubar. The third person is an author of popular folk music for polka dancing, Slavko Avsenik. From this we can conclude that Slovenian biography serves very different cultural interests ranging from elite literary heritage to the broad popular interests related to folklore and popular culture.

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Visual Data Analysis

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h8Knopvy7zU&list=PLjVKITCVnkiaDs9soHWMsINSxwTyB4rxs&index=19>

Abstract

This presentation highlights the role of visual data analysis in supporting research tasks in the field of digital humanities. While interactive data visualization constitutes an important means for presenting data and making results accessible, its potential as an enabling method for supporting data collection and as a tool for analyzing such research data is often not fully exploited. The talk discusses both chances and risks involved in creating interactive visual analysis solutions in the context of digital humanities endeavours and points out prerequisites for their successful realization.

This paper touches upon visual data analysis (which is not so different from data visualization) and the InTaVia project. Of course, projects are about collaboration, also with the humanities, and in this case mainly with history sciences.

First of all, let us talk about visualization in general. *Visualization* is a highly ambiguous term. It is not just *one specific type* of visualization: there are many concepts of it. According to the Oxford Dictionary, “to visualize is to form a mental vision, image, or picture of something etc.” To make visible to the mind or imagination. Of course, if we are creating pictures or images in some way, this also helps to form a mental image, but it's different from what is literally written here. Visualization can also be illustrations. It could be design, it could be photography, there could be other things, like paintings.

It's true, sometimes pictures or images are worth more than a thousand words, but we'll get back to that. We are talking about data visualization here: a very specific type of data visualization, not visualization in general. The idea here is an algorithmic transformation of data into a visual representation. In this case, or in this sense, it is a field of computer science that algorithmically addresses this problem of transformation. This generalizes very nicely, but it might also have downsides, which we will get back to later. Data visualization, as I see it, always includes interactivity; typically, we have these processes like it's nicely outlined in the information visualization reference model below:

Fig. 1: Information visualization model (Card et al., 1999).

So, we have some form of source data, which is transformed into, for example, structured data in the form of tables. Then we add visual information, geometric information that is attached to this data – for example, numbers are going into certain colors or certain positions. That's the idea behind that. Finally, we have view transformations like change of perspective. All of this is finally perceived by a viewer. If there is no such person the whole pipeline makes no sense at all. In that case, you shouldn't do the visualization at all, obviously.

Visualization is interactive; somebody who's watching it can also interfere with these individual stages and, for example, filter and aggregate the data in a transformation step or change the visual mappings, or maybe zoom in or pan etc.

We can also talk about goals such forms of visualization can have. One of the goals is certainly the **presentation** of results or insights retrieved from a project or data one has visualized. Of course, it's important to convey context information – and then there is also the manual enrichment of visualization and data visualization and quality assessment, which are also important. We see that a lot of these automatic processes can sometimes produce erroneous data, so it is very important to provide context for visualization – otherwise, it will be interpreted not in the way we intended.

We could also use interactive visualization as a tool for **knowledge gain**, which is what this paper is talking about: for example, to explore the data we have manually and painfully collected, maybe to analyse it, to build hypotheses, or to check hypotheses we might have about the data. Just to provide a rough framing, the former (presentation) could also be referred to as *reporting* or *storytelling* – or we can use visualization as a *research tool* for our own research. These two fields are overlapping in some way. But we will mainly talk about the second part here.

There is a very famous mantra from Shneiderman (2003), i.e. “overview first, zoom and filter, then details on demand”. It already indicates that we start with showing everything we have, and then we go down into the details. This is one way one could address that and start with the most abstract view as well, and then filter data interactively, show relations within the data,

offer different perspectives. There are some general techniques that are, in one form or another, applied over and over again. They are called *brushing* and *linking* (Becker and Cleveland, 1987); *coordinated views* (Roberts, 2007) can also be used to show, to give different perspectives on the same data. With these two techniques alone, if they are applied in a nice and meaningful way, there are many different analyses we can already make.

A recent project of ours, which has nothing to do with InTaVia, dealt with multi-religious communities in the Middle East during the mediaeval time.

Fig. 2: Project Damast. A case of a coordinated interface with the hierarchy of religious denominations and different religious groups.

In the visuals above (courtesy of Max Franke) We have the spatial representation in form of the map (in the middle), we have a temporal representation shown at the bottom, we have places, which is an important addition to the map because sometimes we don't know anymore where some places were. We can show them on the map so that we have “unplaced” places, so to say (so we need that list). And we have sources, text, confidence annotations of the data. They are very good to have because then we even can show whether we are sure that certain data aspects are valid in some sense, or not.

So, let's start with *highlighting*, *brushing*, *linking* and *filter activation*. With the interface we created for the Damast approach (see Fig. 1), we can interactively pick a certain time frame and then all the data gets automatically filtered through that time frame in the other views as well. Or we could decide to restrict the data to be shown to just a specific source and then it

gets filtered again. Of course, there are many decisions to be made here. For example, we clustered some of the findings of these religious communities – otherwise, the map would be over crowded. But in this case of course it gives a wrong impression so if you uncluster you see that there is actually a lot more data points so to say behind that.

With brushing and filtering, we can already do many different analyses and find all certain things and ask different questions. We can go into detail and also go back to the sources, which is super important to understand where the data comes from. In this case, it allows to answer many different questions like, for example, where are institutions of a specific religion located?

When did they exist in a certain city or place? Are there two specific religious communities collocated in different cities at a certain point in time? These are the questions our colleagues from the historical sciences wanted answered.

Of course, there are also challenges – and chances. I hope I already indicated some of the chances. But there are challenges. There's always uncertainty and abstraction through the algorithmic generation. All the things that go wrong there in the processing steps *before* the visualization will end up in the visualization as well. That's rather natural. There is suboptimal placement of symbols and labels. That's something that also relates to some extent to handmade maps but of course it's even worse if you do that algorithmically because it's just an algorithm that makes certain assumptions and decisions. If we aggregate data, the impression might be very different than if we don't. At the same time, it might give us a clearer overview. This is something we need to be aware about when using such visualizations. There is missing map material. We are covering (in “Damast”) more than 500 years in terms of time span of the collected data; of course, there is no accurate map material for these time spans. So, geographic uncertainties are in there: sometimes we don't know the places; we can have imprecise or wrong depiction of geopolitical entities etc. All of this will end up in your visualization which we need to be aware of – or make our audience aware of. Otherwise, we will be accused of showing wrong things.

There are also chances. We've just indicated how we can do interactive analysis, how we can explore the data, how filtering can take place and hopefully this will help us to get an idea about our data or even help us answer some of the questions we might have. There's also a chance of changing the perspective, maybe even the map projection, or get an idea how people at a certain place would have looked upon the world, so to say. So, these changes of perspective are very easy to comprehend with this kind of interactive visualization.

Is data visualization possible and useful when starting such a project? In most cases, it isn't, actually. I'm fully aware of that. Either it's just not an interesting question you could answer with the [the help of] visualization or the data is by far too difficult to formalize or to address algorithmically in some way.

Then there is a rather small region (and even that is maybe still too big), where this automatic data visualization could come into play and could be worth doing for projects. So that's always an important consideration. And then it is also important to know what to expect from data visualization.

What we typically don't get right away is an answer to our research questions. That would be very surprising, it never worked out, at least so far. But what we can get, and that's super important and also very valuable, is getting ideas about new research questions – or maybe digging into details that are weird or look weird for some reason.

As we've already indicated, this can lead to a lot of problems. It is very important to understand the different research goals when teaming up with computer scientists (or the other way around). Typically, it takes a lot of time to negotiate what all the parties would like to do. And to make this collaboration worthwhile and work and happen in a good way it is also important to find a joint language and discuss the terminology and so on. The terms used here are all ambiguous, which we must be fully aware of.

Working iteratively on the visualization is also very important; simply saying “give me a map of this and that” will yield *something* – but certainly not what is expected. It is important to invest time into these collaborations, all the while paying attention to continuous evaluation and reassessment of goals.

Another challenge is data availability. Either there is digitized data that can be readily used for visualization – or there is not. If it is not, then there are two kinds of approaches available: either **bottom up** (try to develop some infrastructure that helps in terms of creating or curating the data) or **top down** (try to guess what the data will look like and iterate until, with test data, you finally converge in some way). It is reasonable to claim that it is definitely worth thinking about using interfaces and tools like the ones that are briefly depicted in this paper that help to set up and curate the data and manually digitize it with comments and other things.

This will provide more sustainability in terms of creating valuable and sustainable research data. Of course, there are numerous questions we are all aware of: when to publish, copyright issues ... all these things. But with software, visualization software there are also sustainability questions on top of everything else. Should it be open source? Can it be open source? Is it

sustainable to operate and maintain? There are also questions of documentation and traceability of the results: at some point in time it would be really great to get back the data.

As for data confidence, when we are supporting the manual curation steps, comments can be added. There's a possibility in the [Damast] interface to show the conflicting and disputed data. If we have the pipelines in place – rigid pipelines where all the steps are defined – we can record them and do some recording of data and analysis provenance. This is really very interesting because we can create a report of a specific finding or even an appendix automatically for our publication. The report (see Fig. 3) from the Damast system shows, among other things, which kind of filters have been applied.

Fig. 3: Report created in the Damast system. The changes are described in a more or less natural language, containing all the pieces of evidence that indicate which findings went into this report through the different filters, which places were involved, and which sources were used. There is even a depiction of the map that has been created from that.

The report is rather long; we could say it is one uniform super footnote about all the things that have taken place. We are mentioning it because it is not just convenient to have, but the good thing is that we can also use it to go back and have other researchers check our findings. By way of clicking we get back to the electronically generated report and can even show the visualization – and if additional data has been added in the meantime, we can even check out if the findings are still true under this new additional information.

Having these traces of provenance, of analysis provenance can really facilitate the traceability of one's own research, which is valuable per se. In case of the Damast project we were able to publish the data set: it is publicly available in a long term storage at the Stuttgart DaRUS library. The tool is openly accessible and it is also still running at the Humboldt University in Berlin; however, as an expert tool it takes some time to get used to.

To summarize, data visualization – in the sense used here – is an automated process. Interactive data visualization can be a very powerful research tool, but it is important to have realistic expectations of what data visualization with all the collaborations can achieve. Typically, it doesn't solve problems right away. It is also definitely worthwhile considering sustainability, not only of the data, but also of the analyses themselves, which helps make one's research more reproducible.

Case Lake Tuusula – a Prosopographical Demo Using the Storytelling Suite

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I-S7t1tIIQ0&list=PLjvKITCVnkieDs9soHWMsINSxwTyB4rxs&index=21>

Abstract

The presentation focuses on a visual Storytelling Suite that demonstrates the prosopographical network of Finnish artists living in the Lake Tuusula area in the early 20th century. In the case demo, individual cultural heritage objects and person biographies from InTaVia KG are aggregated into a narrative visualization, aiming to provide engaging access to the in/tangible CH data. The presentation also describes technical issues regarding data processing and discusses the resulting visualizations.

The InTaVia storytelling suite has been previously used for creating visual narratives focusing on individual biographies. Here, we decided to focus on a group and create a so-called prosopographical story that would combine multiple actors.

This also provided a chance to discover possibilities and limitations in the InTaVia data. The envisaged outcome was a visualized demonstration that the end users would find engaging. This prosopographical approach hasn't been used previously in InTaVia's stories and projects, so the process was quite exploratory. As a case study, it focused on a particular group, so it naturally has its limitations as its findings are context-dependent. The artist community of Lake Tuusula was selected as the subject of a new narrative case. It consisted of author Juhani Aho, painter Eero Järnefelt, painter Pekka Halonen, author J. H. Erkko, and composer Jean Sibelius and their spouses. They were notable artists who settled in the rural landscape around the Lake Tuusula in the early 1900s. Through their work, they developed and reinforced Finnish culture and self-esteem during politically difficult times. This story was built on the data provided by the InTaVia Knowledge Graph, which consists of semantically linked cultural heritage data in RDF format.

Lake Tuusula Artist Community

Juhani Aho
(1861-1921)

Eero Järnefelt
(1863-1937)

Pekka Halonen
(1865-1933)

J.H Erkko
(1849-1906)

Jean Sibelius
(1865-1957)

Fig. 1: Lake Tuusula artists community.

It was queried and explored by using SPARQL endpoint called YASGUI. Missing information was then added by querying manually new cultural heritage objects and merging those with the existing data. In addition, the story was enriched with additional media elements, such as pictures and music. The data started mining by querying people that were related to Tuusula or Järvenpää, the municipality nearby.

It turned out that in the knowledge graph, there were only two of the community's artists having any connections to the area. That's why a more pragmatic approach was needed; the persons were searched for by filtering the results by their names, which produced all of the artists in the data. Continued exploring showed that the data actually included a lot of the artists' life elements, but information about the place of residence in Tuusula was missing.

However, we proceeded with the technical implementation of the story; we created a collection in the storytelling suite tool that contained all of the artists. The storytelling suite toolkit enabled to create visual biography timelines and depict the largest live events on a map.

Fig. 2: InTaVia storytelling suite tools: an example of Eero Järnefelt's page. The timeline on the left side is automatically generated from the InTaVia data. To make it a bit livelier, a text box was added which contains a short biography and a picture of his self-portrait below it.

However, the initial problem regarding the missing connection to Lake Dusseldorf still remained. It wouldn't make sense to create a prosopographical story without this connection link between the people. And the spatial information was also essential to the structure of the story. As the community around the lake was formed gradually, it seemed most logical to build the story in chronological order and visualize the migration process with the storytelling suite tools.

So, we googled the coordinates of each residence and we manually created cultural heritage objects for them and linked them to the people in the data. And so now we were able to create a nice map view with the storytelling suite, each dot on the map representing an artist's home, and in the final story, they, as well their residents, are presented in chronological order.

Fig. 3: Manually created and georeferenced CH objects.

The goal is to make the knowledge graph-based content a bit more engaging. However, in this case most of the event labels are Finnish, which doesn't provide much information for non-Finnish speakers. This leads to the discussion part.

First, the case demo showed that incomplete or missing information creates a fairly poor starting point for story creation. If the majority of the content has to be added or, for example, translated first manually, the outcome doesn't differ much from a basic slideshow presentation. And the story that ensues itself has its limitations as well, as the slide templates are a bit hard to adjust. Second, the characteristics of prosopography can make story creation a bit tricky. It all starts with fundamental questions such as how does one define a group, what does make a group worth a story to tell, or what do the people in the group have in common. The connecting link might be geographical, as in this example, or something more abstract, such as a shared ideology. So, there is really no one size fits all solution for story creation and visualization. Also, problems caused by data limitations tend to accumulate when groups are involved. If one person is lacking some information, it can be maybe either bypassed or fixed manually, but if all entities in a set of people are missing the information that connects them as a whole, it really can't be ignored. Otherwise, the outcome would be just the same as a sequence of separate biographies. And that would also make the story quite lengthy.

To address both of these previously mentioned aspects, I propose a network-based approach to story creation. So at least theoretically, interesting groups and collectivity could be studied by

conducting social network analysis in the InTaVia data. In addition, this kind of visualizations could be a nice way to illustrate relationships within the group.

For example, in the Lake Tuusula community, Aino Sibelius was the wife of Jean Sibelius, but also the sister of Eero Järnefelt and a former crush of Juhani Aho. This kind of network visualization is supported by storytelling suite as well. But once again, we ran into data constraints here. Only two of the relations that are illustrated here are available in the knowledge graph. So, while the Storytelling Institute offers a nice set of tools for story creation, it cannot be used as a standalone solution. At least for this group of artists, as manual work is needed in order to make the data and the story complete.

Cultural Heritage Data as Humanities Research Data

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Do1WkvxkUYM&list=PLjVKITCVnkieDs9soHWMsINSxwTyB4rxs&index=22>

Abstract

European commission Recommendation of 10.11.2021 is focusing on common European data space for cultural heritage, emphasizing Europeana strategy 2020-2025 to empower digital change of European cultural heritage institutions and support their digital transformation. Work is being done towards implementation and development of heritage science where humanities research data is our common ground for transdisciplinary research in the Open Science environment. This presentation covers different aspects of such environment and some best practice solutions in the field, where InTaVia project is most certainly one of them.

Digitization evolution overview

This contribution comes from the perspective of a national library, working as aggregator of Europeana, but also considering development of research in the European data space. For this reason, let's start with few words on where we are with transformation of digitization culture and digital environment on the national and international level. First digitization projects started in earnest in the 1990s and the first decade we also mark as the first generation of the digitization. Between the year 2000 and 2020 the second generation of digitisation took place. During this ensuing phase mass digitization was implemented in most European countries and in different institutions, especially millions of pages of the written cultural heritage was digitized.

We are now in the midst of the third generation of digitization where focus is on 3D and other cultural contents such as sound and vision, but also on accessibility and usage of content (for example IIIF has become a "must-have" standard). Use of digitized content is also developing and science is extracting and combining different data from diverse GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, museums and archives) in common research. We are merging the data making the link between different databases, metadata etc. to make the already digitized content useful and reused by different fields of science and education. This way we are building heritage science within one field of research as well as between different areas of science by linking the data between different cultural and heritage research fields, particularly for example

with implementation of natural sciences such as chemistry into transdisciplinary interaction with humanities.

Forms of the cultural heritage

There are three main relevant forms of (written) cultural heritage today in GLAM institutions. On one side, we have the physical heritage – physical objects of traditional forms of heritage such as manuscripts on parchment, paper documents, cassette tapes (VHS and audio), maps, pictures etc. The physical heritage has specific requirements for storage, access and use. By means of digitisation many issues arising from its preservation and accessibility can be addressed, but also others such as ethical and copyright issues occur.

On the other side, we have digital heritage comprised of digitized historical documents – digital twins of the original physical heritage – and digitally born heritage developed today, including web pages and social media content.¹ All these forms of digital heritage can constitute data collections for research (in humanities and beyond).

All these different forms of heritage can be searched through one common interface, allowing heritage access and reuse, but of course the content has to be linked and integrated through common identification and cataloguing systems, allowing heritage identification, preservation as well as licensing.

The case of the Digital Library of Slovenia

In Slovenia, the Digital Library of Slovenia² was developed by the National and University Library in 2006 with support of Norway Grants.³ In 2022, after 15 years of work, the Digital library of Slovenia reached its milestone of one million objects.⁴ From 2009 the National Library of Slovenia is also national aggregator and a trusted partner of Europeana. Objects published on Digital Library of Slovenia are very diverse, ranging from all sorts of written cultural heritage to 3D objects and other contents like music, video or visual data.

Content is being produced with integration, cooperation, and linking between institutions, and between data related contents. Until 2023 cooperation was established with altogether 660 institutions from all over Slovenia – from public to private sector.⁵

¹ See <https://netpreserve.org/> and <https://arhiv.nuk.uni-lj.si/>.

² See <https://www.dlib.si/>.

³ See <https://www.norwaygrants.si/en/>.

⁴ In country of two million inhabitants.

⁵ See <http://www.agregator.si/>.

And how the content is presented to the audiences and how audiences are approached to engage with content in the Digital Library of Slovenia? Primarily, metadata with full texts of each object is published open source and digital data is referenced with Uniform Resource Name (URN) and persistent unique identifiers (PIDs), linking metadata of each digitized subject/item with catalogue data and personal (authorial) data as well as content. Furthermore, transcriptions and georeferencing are implemented. This way different collections and digital stories are being build, which can further be used in secondary purposes where participatory approaches to digital cultural heritage are being used for driving engagement. E-learning tools and materials for education, training and research can be created such as quizzes and online games, online classrooms (for example Cankar's universe)⁶ or online exhibitions (for example Cartographic Treasures of the National and University Library).⁷

Building the common European data space for cultural heritage

Until 2023 already a vast network of Europeana national, regional, domain and thematic aggregators was established for data sharing and exchange of knowledge and best practices in aggregation.⁸

With European commission Recommendation of 10.11.2021 on common European data space for cultural heritage also the digital transformation of Europe's heritage sector was accelerated. Deployment of the common European data space for cultural heritage is taking place to foster the reuse of cultural heritage content and the digital cultural landscape is changing even further. Already developed digital collections, such as the Digital Library of Slovenia, are evolving.

⁶ See <https://cankar.dlib.si/#event-ivan-cankar>.

⁷ See <https://www.nuk.uni-lj.si/Kartografski-zakladi-nuk>.

⁸ See <https://pro.europeana.eu/tags/aggregators-forum>.

Fig. 1. Building the common European data space for cultural heritage, Recommendation of 10.11.2021 on a common European data space for cultural heritage. Source: <https://www.slideshare.net/Europeana/french-presidency-1-march-2022>

New initiatives such as the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) are emerging on international level, and in Europeana “decentralisation, openness and interoperability are ever more important to our work”.⁹ Namely, today we have a huge ecosystem of different data, tools, infrastructures, projects, institutions, and last but not least also different users – from individual researchers to institutional ones (institutions build their own databases, projects form their own research collections). Such way there are huge amounts of content very difficult for the final user to find and reach.

One big data space for cultural heritage has thus become essential for humanities and transdisciplinary research in heritage science – on international but also on national level. Such data space can further be developed in a “digital infrastructure aimed more specifically at heritage professionals, scientists and researchers to access advanced digitisation tools and services for conservation and preservation.”¹⁰

⁹ See <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/the-data-space-and-the-collaborative-cloud-cooperation-for-mutual-and-collective-benefit>.

¹⁰ Ibid.

Moving towards 2030 or what do we need to effectively manage the (written) cultural heritage in the 21st century?

Based on the Recommendations from the European Commission on data spaces, European countries are now working on the TwinIt! 3D action, i.e. on the digitization of 3D objects and facilitating the digitization in museums and other collections where digitization was not as well integrated as in the libraries.

But to support, develop and integrate all sorts of tangible and intangible heritage in a common (national/international) clouds there are still many open issues to be addressed. First, not all heritage data is accessible in digital environment. There are still huge differences between organisations and European countries. The backbones – metadata systems (databases/catalogues of heritage) with (even basic) heritage objects data are missing in many cases.

Second, standards and protocols for publishing digital heritage other than 2D/written are also still evolving and uniform long-term preservation, access and use of, for example 3D digital heritage, is still being build up.

Third, common digital heritage infrastructures are not in place on national levels to make diverse heritage accessible and searchable from one starting point (one entry point to all contents) for the final users in order for them to find the content they need. For example, when searching for a person, they would also be able to get information about the place where that person lived, along with the contents that person was involved with, e.g. writings, visualized canvases or anything of the like, all combined in one related space.

Moving towards the 2030 we would need to uptake basic strategic measures in direction of a common European data space with heritage data usable in culture and science:

- Building common, connected and standardized (national and international) e-infrastructures of Cultural Heritage Data – such as ECCCH (or as in case of Slovenia a national SCCCH – Slovenian national collaborative cloud for cultural heritage);
- Implementing uniform and standardised models of metadata, standards and protocols as well as workflows for diverse GLAM institutions;
- Developing sustainable national and international Cultural Heritage Data strategies for support of heritage science with long term access and preservation plans.

Furthermore, not only on national level and through Europeana on international one, to enable heritage users to reach the heritage content and reuse it in research, innovation and tourism or similar economic purposes to “generate new jobs not only in the cultural heritage sector but also in other cultural and creative sectors, including for instance the video game and film

industries,” already well established European digital infrastructures should be connected and integrated into the work of GLAM institutions (where still not), offering further deployment of heritage data for better support of research.

There is DARIAH as a digital humanities infrastructure,¹¹ CLARIN infrastructure for research based on language resources,¹² OPERAS for publication access,¹³ and E-RIHS infrastructure for heritage science transdisciplinary work.¹⁴

And additionally, if GLAM institutions want – if *we* want – to deploy our collections and results better, we also have to integrate heritage data in other nodes and hubs where data can be further reused by other researchers and other audiences. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹⁵ is one of the options where also heritage data could be published as Humanities Research Data and the newly developed European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage will be next possibility GLAMs will have a chance to use.

¹¹ See <https://www.dariah.eu/>.

¹² See <https://www.clarin.eu/>.

¹³ See <https://operas-eu.org/>.

¹⁴ See <https://www.e-rihs.si/>.

¹⁵ See <https://eosc-portal.eu/>.

Beyond InTaVia: Storytelling in Related Projects

Videolecture:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nRBJNp0MIg4&list=PLjVKITCVnkieDs9soHWMsINSxwTyB4rxs&index=20>

Abstract

This talk addresses the Horizon Europe MEMORISE project, which is developing storytelling solutions to preserve memories of Nazi persecution and make them intuitively accessible to a public audience. We shall also look into the initial plan to incorporate storytelling techniques into the American Pictures Digital project.

The purpose of visualization, as we see it, is the connection between domain experts with the data to allow them to analyse data, to get some new insight, some new perspective, also quantitative means. It is a kind of a connection between domain expertise, domain knowledge and computer science. The most convenient thing is to work with something that is intuitively visual. Now when we talk about storytelling, it goes a little bit further in my point of view.

We have seen in some projects that if those tools were given to causal users, not much would come out of that, despite their huge potential. So, when we talk about storytelling, we talk about how we can make scientific results accessible to people outside the expert community. This is something we have done with InTaVia.

Building Bridges with Visualization

Fig. 1: Screenshot of the InTaVia visual analytics studio (left) and the storytelling suite (right). It is consistent of a creator and a viewer component.

Whereas the creator looks a little bit more challenging to operate, the viewer is a possibility for users to consume stories. The users would not be the domain experts but rather those interested in the stories we want to tell. Looking at Segal and Harris' definition of storytelling, it starts like a continuum between what they called reader-driven storytelling and author-driven storytelling. The reader-driven storytelling, is something we can do with a visual analytics studio because we have all different visualizations and we can somewhat browse interactively, we can say design our own story. Author driven storytelling is when e.g. a domain expert designs a story and has a clear, straight path for the consumer to consume or to get the story.

Now for some related projects running at SDU; we will take a look at three different projects of different maturity: **Museology**, an unfunded project that Jakob Kusnick is mainly working on in collaboration with musicologists; the Memorise project, an EU Horizon Europe project; and **American Pictures Digital**, a project that we are still seeking funding for.

Museology is, in essence, very similar to InTaVia, but focusing on a particular area: sustainable instrument making. We have a visual exploration interface that allows us to browse instruments used in orchestras based on different features but with a focus on what resources instruments are made of. It allows us to see the tree species and their threat statuses to get an idea whether an instrument is a sustainable instrument that can be produced in the future – or should we find alternative resources because the tree an instrument is made of is under threat of extinction.

Fig. 2: Museology project.

One of the projects we have done in this context was a virtual reconstruction of the Bernburg Euthanasia Centre, a very quick walkthrough with 20 annotation points to tell a story. A sort of a virtual visit of the killing institution. It is a contemporary model of the facility; we can add some things that are not existent anymore, like the crematory that is not existent anymore, but we can add some dull models into the existing one. The story told here is just like what the guide would tell you when he or she would walk you through the facility. But here our idea is to enhance these stories or to create new stories because we have a lot of testimonies or interviews done in the 1960s with the staff who worked at the facility.

All of the people brought to the facility, around 14.000, were actually killed, so there's very few little information about the victims. However, there is a lot of information from the interviews with the staff, so how the whole process works. They were conducted in the 1960s; we can use them so as to not be guided through the memorial site by a guide but rather let the doctors or the nurses do the tour of the facility.

This is creating new experiences. It might be intense, so we have to evaluate what comes out of this before we let the general public experience it. But this is what Memorise is doing: it tries to connect memories or personal experiences with space and time.

Let us also briefly mention the **American Pictures Digital** project. American Pictures is a "book" with a lot of photographs from the United States by Jacob Holdt. Jacob Holt has been travelling the United States in the 1970s, and he made a lot of photographs. He documented his experiences in the United States. He lived together with poor black people. He lived together with people from the Ku Klux Klan. He lived together with, or visited the Rockefellers. So, he had a lot of impressions about living together, about social inequality, about exclusion, oppression – all the social ills that belong(ed) to the American society, especially in the 1970s. The 70s tour took him one or two years and he took some 16.000 during the time. After, he revisited the United States and gave lectures.

He gave around 7.000 lectures at universities and schools about his experiences, going very quickly through the biographies of the people he visited (and later revisited) to tell their stories. His lectures were a very inclusive experience, pointing out the state of our society. However, it is not about pointing fingers, but instead about drawing relations between the poor black and the poor white population, among them the Klan people, who are, as he says, generally poor. The general idea of this project is to preserve the way these stories are told. Holdt is 76 or 77 now, so he has reduced, of course, the number of lectures he gives. He gives a lot of lectures at

Danish schools these days. He started writing on Instagram about his pictures, picking a picture and writing about his experiences, his memories about what's on these pictures.

We want to somehow bring together all of his knowledge. The photographs are digitized. We do not necessarily have dates and places associated with all the photographs, which is going to be tricky. We have diaries, we have postcards, audios, videos, we have lots of multi modal data resources. The question we will target in this project is to digitize the sources that are not digitized yet. How can we integrate his memories, because he has lots of anecdotes in his mind, so he will tell us lots of stories that are not necessarily written on a postcard or somewhere else. How can we connect these resources? How can we connect information on a postcard with a photograph, for instance? What is most important, we want to create a learning environment for schools because we want to somehow create a new experience that survives for longer.

In conclusion: what are the future challenges of storytelling? Maybe we can create something like a reader-as-author driven storytelling. With the use of AI, maybe we can create semi-curated stories that work and that keep you engaged in the theme. Maybe we can create more immersive experiences to relate cultural heritage to the space we walk, to the time we are in at the moment. For cultural institutions reproducibility is important: can I create a framework that can be adopted by different cultural heritage institutions with no or not easily diversity-aware cultural heritage experiences? Cultural heritage experiences need to be somehow diversity-aware for different or for diverse audiences. Lastly, maybe we can create – at some point in time – storytelling and digital tools that keep *everyone* active and engaged when dealing with cultural heritage. Something that works for a six-year-old as well as an attentive old lady or an expert.